

On the Study of Bismuth Phosphate as a Carrier for Tetravalent Actinides

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In presence of an excess of bismuth, an unstable form of bismuth phosphate takes up UX_1 through mixed crystal formation even in presence of finite quantities of thorium. That the host lattice is unstable has been demonstrated by determining λ values at intervals of time after the addition of reactants. Even after fifteen minutes, the constancy of heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) has been found to disappear; it does not obey the homogeneous distribution law on prolonged equilibration. Zr^{95} and Ni^{95} are taken up through adsorption by the host lattice which does not take up any appreciable amount of rare earth or yttrium activities. A laboratory procedure of separating tetravalent actinides from the trivalent ones has been developed. Both stable and unstable forms of bismuth phosphate have been found to take up zirconium through adsorption. Amongst the possible coseparating components, it is only the tetravalent actinides which are taken up by an unstable form of bismuth phosphate through mixed crystal formation

Bismuth phosphate was used by earlier workers as a carrier of plutonium for separating it from large amounts of uranium. Though it was used in a large-scale separation plant, the mechanism of the uptake is still unknown. The condition under which previous workers used it as a coseparating agent brought along with it considerable amounts of fission products. The object of the present investigation is to study the mechanism of the uptake of tetravalent actinides of such a faithful carrier and to find out conditions for minimising the amount of fission products that coseparate with bismuth phosphate. It has been observed by workers in this laboratory that a freshly formed precipitate in some cases behaves differently as regards the nature of the uptake from aged samples. If the same phenomenon occurred in the case of bismuth phosphate, it would be possible to eliminate some of the fission products and the mechanism of uptake may be clarified. UX_1 was taken as a representative for tetravalent actinides.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents used, such as bismuth oxide, phosphoric acid, etc., were all of AnalaR quality. $Eu^{152,154}$ and Y^{91} were supplied by A. E. R. E., Harwell, England. Carrier-free UX_1 was prepared from uranium in this laboratory¹. The heterogeneous distribution law was verified under different experimental conditions.

(a). A preliminary study was made by taking a solution of bismuth nitrate in nitric acid and adding phosphoric acid slowly so that the precipitation did not take place during the time of addition. On stirring, the supersaturation was broken. This condition is

1. Purkayastha and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 429.

suitable for the verification of the heterogeneous distribution factor. The precipitate was washed with very dilute nitric acid. The naphthalene bed containing the bismuth phosphate was transferred to a weighed porcelain basin, heated at 350° to a constant weight, and the activity remaining in the solution was measured by a liquid counter. This preliminary study had disadvantages.

(b) A better and more simplified procedure was adopted to crystallise bismuth phosphate from a homogeneous solution. Bismuth nitrate solution in nitric acid, impregnated with UX_1 activity, was taken in an L-shaped tube and kept inside a thermostat. The vertical portion of the tube was fixed to a mechanical shaker. Dilute phosphoric acid in a different container was kept in the same thermostat till it reached the thermostat temperature. Phosphoric acid was then added to the bismuth nitrate solution. Care was taken so that the volume remained 100 ml and the final acidity with respect to nitric acid was 1*N*. Some time was allowed for a thorough mixing. The supersaturation was then broken by shaking the system with a mechanical arrangement having 60 to 70 vibrations per min. It was then shaken for 5 min. A portion of the solution was filtered through a naphthalene bed. Bismuth and UX_1 activity were measured from the solution.

(c). In the third procedure, bismuth phosphate from 1*N*- HNO_3 medium was precipitated by dropping dilute phosphoric acid from a pipette. The system was under constant stirring. The rest of the procedure was as in (b).

Niobium pentoxide was fused with potassium carbonate and potassium fluoride. The melt was taken in water and the carbonate was neutralised by HF. Zr^{95} in equilibrium with its daughter Nb^{95} was supplied in a carrier-free state by Messrs Philips Duphar in oxalic acid solution. In a study of the uptake of Zr and Nb by bismuth phosphate, the same procedure as was used in the case of UX_1 was followed. Zirconium and niobium activities were added in a carrier-free state. In the case of measuring the activity, natural zirconium and niobium were added to act as the carrier and the holdback-carrier respectively. Zirconium was separated as barium fluozirconate. This last precipitate was washed with dilute HF till free of niobium. The precipitate was then dissolved in HCl and the zirconium activity was measured from this solution. The niobium activity was computed by deducting the zirconium activity from the total activity added. *D* and λ are calculated from the following expressions. Data are recorded in Tables I-IV.

$$D = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solid}}}{\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}}\right)_{\text{solution}}}$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\log \left(\frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}}\right)}{\log \left(\frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}}\right)}$$

TABLE I

*Coprecipitation of UX₁ with bismuth phosphate at 35° in 1N-HNO₃.*Initial bismuth concentration = $2.147 \times 10^{-2} M$.

	%Bi pptd.	%UX ₁ carried.	λ. Th added. (g./100 ml).	D.
(a) Series.		1. Period of shaking = 5 min.		
	16.5	41.4	2.96	3.58
	20.3	49.7	3.02	3.8
	31.9	66.3	2.84	4.2
	42.4	80.6	2.97	5.64
			Av. 2.94	
		(2) Period of shaking = 4 days.		
	20.1	26.7		1.45
	25.8	40.6		1.87
	33.3	54.5		2.40
	37.8	77.3		5.6
(b) Series.		1. Period of shaking = 5 min.		
	11.67	28.59	2.71	2.03
	18.86	43.74	2.75	3.34
	25.24	54.54	2.70	3.55
	25.24	54.58	2.71	3.56
			Av. 2.717	
		2. Period of shaking = 15 min.		
	14.14	49.05	4.40	5.85
	21.61	55.61	3.34	4.54
	29.29	60.66	2.70	3.72
		3. Period of shaking = 5 min.		
(i)	14.47	37.88	0.0024	3.05
(ii)	17.44	42.14	0.0048	2.86
(iii)	21.09	40.93	0.0240	2.22
(iv)	17.34	38.76	0.0362	2.57
(v)	9.31	18.17	0.0240	2.05
	17.94	40.05	0.0240	2.59
	20.53	47.22	0.0240	2.78
	27.41	48.59	0.0240	2.07
			Av. 2.37	
(c) Series.		Period of shaking = 5 min. Bi = $3.6 \times 10^{-2} M$.		
	10.55	43.95	5.19	6.66
	15.72	60.37	5.41	8.17
	23.30	75.20	5.26	9.98
			Av. 5.28	

TABLE II

Coprecipitation of Eu¹⁵² and Y⁹¹ with bismuth phosphate at 35°.
Initial Bi conc. = $2.96 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Conc. of HNO ₃ .	Tracer used.	Contact period.	%Bi.	%Tracer separated.		D.
				(a).	(b).	
1.0N	Eu	5 min.	31.0	0.035		
1.0	Eu	5	63.4	0.091		
1.0	Eu	5	94.5	0.510		
1.0	Eu	5	99.0	0.620		
1.0	Eu	4 days	48.6		13.1	0.160
1.0	Eu	4	70.0		19.3	0.094
1.0	Eu	4	87.7		33.0	0.069
2.0	Eu	5 min	40.5	0.220		
2.0	Eu		68.9	0.500		
0.2	Eu		94.5	2.100		
0.1	Eu		94.5	2.010		
0.2	*Eu		100.0	92.500		
0.2	*Eu	30	100.0	90.600		
1.0	Y	5	33.3	0.006		
1.0	Y		67.6	0.048		

N.B. (a) with freshly formed host lattice, (b) with aged host lattice.

In case where uptake is of a very low order, very high counts (80,000-800,000 per min.) were used. The precipitated bismuth phosphate was filtered, dissolved in about 8N -HNO₃ and the activity measured with a liquid counter.

*The concentration of phosphoric acid in this case was 20 times higher than that of bismuth.

TABLE III

Coprecipitation of Zr⁹⁵ and Nb⁹⁵ with preformed bismuth phosphate at 35° in N-HNO₃.

Time.	% Bi pptd.	%Total activity carried.	%Zr activity carried.	D for Zr.	%Nb activity carried.	D for Nb.
24 hr.	10	55.73	..	..	..	..
48	10	65.54	27.34	15.82	38.20	18.19
72	10	64.99	30.76	22.82	34.23	13.47
96	10	64.82	28.99	18.77	35.83	15.16
120	10	69.11	29.13	19.05	39.98	21.00

N. B. Bismuth phosphate was prepared by adding phosphoric acid to bismuth nitrate solution. It was then washed and dried at about 300° till constant weight and powdered and filtered through 120 mesh.

TABLE IV

Co-precipitation of Zr⁹⁵ and Nb⁹⁵ with bismuth phosphate at 35° in N-HNO₃.

Initial Bi conc. = (ca.) $2.147 \times 10^{-2} M$.

%Bi pptd.	%Zr carried.	λ for Zr.	D for Zr.	%Nb carried.	λ for Nb.	D for Nb.
(a) Period of shaking = 5 min.						
7.68	26.46	12.00		47.52	22.30	
10.75	27.48	9.00		52.13	21.40	
18.94	29.35	5.50		55.76	17.80	
24.16	31.61	4.83		52.17	8.85	
(b) Period of shaking = 4 days.						
5.135	62.97		31.43	60.91		28.8
11.450	65.02		14.36	73.57		21.5
20.780	74.91		11.39	77.50		13.1

*The experiment was carried out with preformed bismuth phosphate.

DISCUSSION

It should be mentioned at the outset that three different procedures were adopted to examine the constancy of the heterogeneous distribution factor. Table I shows that this factor, λ , comes out constant in all these procedures. Bismuth phosphate therefore takes up UX_1 through mixed crystal formation. This finding has been verified at finite concentrations of thorium (Table I, b-series-3). In the internally formed system, when freshly precipitated bismuth phosphate containing the tracer was equilibrated with the mother liquor (Table I, a-series-2) for a period of 4 days, the homogeneous distribution factor, D , was not found constant. Even if we shake an internally formed system for 15 min., the constancy of λ also vanishes (Table I, b-series-2). This type of discrepancy, described in a previous communication, is due to a difference in the morphology. It can therefore be concluded that when kept in contact with the solution, bismuth phosphate undergoes a change in the morphology. The diminishing trend in λ values as shown in Table I (b-series-2) clearly indicates that the host lattice is very unstable and it decomposes within 15 min. to the stable form which does not take up any UX_1 activity through mixed crystal formation. A considerable amount of UX_1 activity was taken up through adsorption.

The question naturally arises whether this unstable host component, which takes up UX_1 or tetravalent actinides through mixed crystal formation, can be made specific in the routine separation procedure. In an earlier study by Seaborg *et al.*², it has been shown that even an aged bismuth phosphate precipitate can be used as a coseparating host component which carries only zirconium, niobium, rare earth, and yttrium activities. But their study refers to an aged bismuth phosphate which according to our observation takes up tetravalent actinide (on the assumption that UX_1 is a representative of tetravalent actinide). Attempts have also been made to separate UX_1 (tetravalent actinides) eliminating the fission products with a freshly formed bismuth phosphate where the uptake in question takes place through mixed crystal formation. On the assumption that the partition factor is 5.3, when UX_1 is carried with bismuth phosphate by dropping phosphoric acid from a comparatively concentrated solution, near about cent per cent of UX_1 is coprecipitated, whereas about 65% of bismuth is precipitated. The trivalent rare earths, yttrium, and trivalent actinides may be completely eliminated (Table II) if we coseparate the tetravalent actinide with bismuth phosphate by a dropwise addition of phosphoric acid, keeping some amount of bismuth in solution. Earlier workers²⁻⁴ used an excess of phosphoric acid for the precipitation of bismuth phosphate. At a lower acid concentration, bismuth phosphate has been found to carry even 100% of rare earth or trivalent actinide activities, if the precipitation is made with an excess phosphoric acid. It has also been observed that when bismuth is precipitated at a low-acid concentration (0.2*N*-HNO₃) by the addition of just the sufficient amount of phosphoric acid, only about 2% uptake of europium takes place. An excess of the phosphate ion should therefore be avoided for the separation of tetravalent actinides from rare earths. The best condition for the separation of tetravalent one should therefore be the precipitation of bismuth phosphate from about 1*N*-HNO₃ by dropwise

2. Thomson and Seaborg, "Progress in Nuclear Energy", Series III, Process Chemistry, Volume 1, p. 163.
3. McLane and Peterson, paper 19.3 of "The Transuranium Elements", National Nuclear Energy Series, Division IV, volume-14B, McGraw-Hill Book Company Inc., New York, 1949.
4. Rydberg, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 1252.

addition of phosphoric acid, keeping some bismuth (15% in solution) avoiding an excess of the phosphoric acid and minimising the period of contact of the tracer with the host component (Table I, c-series).

The question naturally arises whether zirconium or niobium activities, which appear as fission products, can be eliminated like rare earth or trivalent actinides by a newly formed bismuth phosphate. A coseparation study with Zr^{95} and its daughter Nb^{95} , both in an internally and an externally formed system (Table IV), reveals that a considerable amount of these two is taken up by the host component, irrespective of the method of precipitation of the host lattice. The uptake does not follow either the homogeneous or the heterogeneous distribution law. In the case of an externally formed host lattice, we determined the time for attainment of the equilibrium. It has been found that the equilibrium is attained within two days. In determining the distribution factor in the preformed system, we equilibrated the system for four days with different quantities of the solid phase. Table IV shows that the homogeneous distribution factor does not come out constant both in the case of zirconium and of niobium. But the extent of the uptake in both the cases is considerably high. A high uptake has also been observed in the case of a freshly formed bismuth phosphate. As a coseparating agent of tetravalent actinides, bismuth phosphate loses here its specificity. In the separation of fission products, only the tetravalent actinides are taken up by bismuth phosphate through mixed crystal formation under specific conditions and this provides an easy method of eliminating the trivalent actinides and the rare earths.

Incidentally, a simple coseparation study, as has been described, not only offers some idea of the mechanism of the uptake but also helps us in finding a way to obtain the pure component free from many of the associates through unstable host components.